

Research Article

Malaysia Logistics Platform (MLP) Trading App

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Abstract: The team developed the Malaysia Logistics Platform (MLP), a trading application that acts as an intermediary for logistics purposes. MLP aims to help foreign and local businesses locate logistics services in Malaysia and offers affordable shipping options. To access MLP, users are required to sign up with their business email and password. The menu offers options for transportation modes (sea, land, or air) and logistics locators. For example, selecting sea transportation displays available local sea logistics industries or ports in Malaysia. Then, users can directly book shipping services and make payments online. Lastly, the app notifies the logistics providers upon payment, securing the transaction. MLP's commercial potential is that it connects businesses with transport providers, increases efficiency by matching supply and demand, and generates revenue through transaction fees and subscriptions. MLP contributes to business by simplifying shipping processes, locating nearby logistics providers, and offering affordable transport services. In conclusion, MLP enhances the local economy, improves logistics efficiency, and generates income.

Keywords: trading application; logistics

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1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, Malaysia has positioned itself as a major player in the logistics sector, which is vast and diverse. It leverages its strategic geographical location to support a growing number of trade and supply chains. With the surge of e-commerce, international trade, and the growing importance of supply chain efficiency, there is a strong demand for reliable and cost-effective logistics solutions. This includes improvements in infrastructure and rising freight volumes since the logistics industry is the backbone of Malaysia's supply chain ecosystem. (MIDA,2023).

However, finding the right logistics providers is challenging because of the complexity and fragmentation of the industry, where numerous providers operate independently with their systems and procedures. This makes it difficult, especially for small to medium-sized businesses or international companies, to connect with logistics providers to fit their specific needs and international shipping

requirements. Therefore, the Malaysia Logistics Platform (MLP), an intermediary trading app, was created to meet the growing demand for logistics services that are affordable and easy to access. It helps local and foreign businesses to directly interact with logistics providers across different transportation modes such as sea, land, or air, enabling the efficiency of Malaysia's logistics industry and providing a centralized platform that benefits both service providers and users. MLP earns revenue from transaction fees, subscriptions, and collaboration with logistics providers, which helps in sustaining operations while supporting the economy.

These are the ways on how to use the app. Firstly, users are required to sign in with their business email and password, which ensures that the platform is used by verified business entities. If a business does not have an account in MLP, they can create an account as a user and sign in to the app to access it. For the second step, once logged in, users can select a transportation mode based on their preferences, such as sea, land, or air. For example, clicking "sea" displays options for local sea logistics providers and ports in Malaysia. Next, users can locate service providers that are available by browsing the options in selected regions or areas, making it easy to identify nearby services. Then, the app will display a list of companies (providers) according to the selected area. After selecting a provider, users can directly book through MLP and perform online payments via FPX Online Banking or Credit/Debit Card, streamlining the process to avoid delays. Upon payment, MLP will automatically notify the logistics provider, securing and confirming the transaction.

1.1 Problem Statement

The invention of the Malaysia Logistics Platform (MLP) addresses a critical gap in the logistics industry, specifically the lack of a unified platform capable of effortlessly connecting businesses with the most suitable logistics services across multiple transportation modes such as sea, land, and air, leading to inefficiencies, miscommunication, and increased costs. This disjointed system makes it difficult for businesses to compare and select the most cost-effective and efficient logistics solutions.

Logistics providers themselves face challenges under the current setup, as they lack a modernized mechanism to effectively market their services to a wider audience. Without a centralized platform, providers struggle to reach potential customers, leading to underutilization of their services and difficulties in securing bookings. This inefficiency in customer outreach further interferes with the overall effectiveness of the logistics ecosystem.

The Malaysia Logistics Platform (MLP) resolves these issues by offering a comprehensive, one-stop solution. It enables businesses to easily search for, compare, reserve, and pay for logistics services through a single platform, regardless of transportation mode. By simplifying the process of locating the best logistics options, MLP raises the efficiency and cost-effectiveness of the entire logistics process. Not only does it reduce the operational burdens on businesses, but it also improves the visibility and accessibility of logistics providers, helping them to optimize their capacity and secure bookings more efficiently.

1.2 Objectives

The Malaysia Logistics Platform (MLP) is an innovative trading application designed to connect local and foreign businesses with Malaysia's logistics services. MLP functions as a centralized platform that simplifies and optimizes accessibility to logistics and supply chain processes for providers and users. MLP objectives are to:

1. **Connect Businesses with Reliable Logistics Providers:** MLP will act as an intermediary for local and foreign businesses, allowing easy access to a variety of logistics services across different modes of transportation, including both small and large local providers.
2. **Enhance Transparency and Accessibility:** MLP aims to provide a user-friendly experience with accessibility to detailed company information, reviews, and price comparisons of logistics providers.
3. **Facilitate Secure and Efficient Transactions:** MLP will ensure a secure and seamless experience from booking to payment processes by integrating online payment systems with instant notifications provided upon payment confirmation.
4. **Boost the Local Economy and Promote International Trade:** MLP will strengthen the local economy by collaborating with logistics partners to facilitate trade businesses and provide trustworthy channels for business transactions, encouraging more businesses to engage with local influence in the global supply chain.

2. NOVELTY

The Malaysia Logistics Platform (MLP) is an innovative and first-mover advantage of trading application that connects both local and foreign logistics businesses in Malaysia by offering seamless way to manage and book transportation services by various modes of transportation. MLP's outstanding feature is its locator tool that allows users to easily identify, connect, and partner with the right logistics providers that are filtered based on their preferences.

Besides that, MLP provides real-time messaging and AI technology that ensure immediate, reliable updates between users and logistics providers. It enhances customer support, enables prompt issue resolution, and helps to create a dependable and streamlined logistics experience. MLP is compatible with Android, iOS, PC, and other tablet devices, which makes it accessible across various platforms for maximum flexibility and convenience. The app is designed with a user-friendly interface that ensures easy installation and navigation for logistics companies of all sizes.

As the first app of its kind to enter the Malaysian market, MLP offers a unique advantage to logistics companies and users to optimize operations in ways that weren't previously possible.

3. COMMERCIALIZATION POTENTIAL

Connecting businesses with logistics providers in a decentralized market like Malaysia might lead to several difficulties. Businesses, especially foreign companies unfamiliar with the local logistics landscape, often struggle to find reliable and efficient transportation alternatives. To overcome these issues and increase efficiency, a centralized platform is needed.

This app's commercial potential is that it connects businesses with transport providers, increasing efficiency by matching supply and demand. MLP has substantial commercialization potential in the logistics and transportation industry. Firstly, it enhances operational efficiency by streamlining the process of connecting businesses with logistics providers. MLP provides a centralized platform where companies can choose transportation options and booking services, simplifying the process of finding trustworthy logistics providers, particularly for international businesses that are unfamiliar with the Malaysian market.

Next, MLP has the potential to drive economic growth within Malaysia by supporting the local logistics sector. By linking businesses with local transport providers, the platform fosters more business activity in Malaysia and strengthens the domestic logistics industry. It also offers affordable and reliable transport options, helping local businesses compete better in the global market.

Moreover, MLP contributes to high privacy and user concerns by providing secured online payment options to ensure that there is no data exposed to third parties. The app also includes the company's profile, contact information, and headquarters locations of all logistics providers, including direct lines for any inquiries and assistance.

Lastly, MLP generates income through subscriptions, transaction fees, and collaborating with logistics providers.

4. BENEFIT TO USER

Malaysia Logistics Platform (MLP) offers numerous advantages to the user upon its introduction to the market. Firstly, broadened business greater access to efficient transport services allows local and foreign businesses to grow their operations without having to worry about issues with logistics.

Secondly, enhanced effectiveness by optimizing the whole shipping process, MLP minimizes significant time and effort for companies, and it is more efficient and cheaper operations (Tomas Kregzde, 2023). Instead of spending hours or days looking for logistics providers to track bookings, businesses can utilize MLP to identify, book, and pay for services quickly and conveniently. This helps companies to run more easily since they no longer have to worry about delays or complicated preparations. Hence, it further enhances the whole supply chain, enabling companies to deliver their products to market more quickly and cost-effectively.

Moreover, the app offers real-time help for transportation questions and advice, which is especially valuable for small company owners that are unfamiliar with logistics. Tracking and push alerts ensure consumers receive timely shipping information and may alter plans using the app. They offer convenience and comfort of mind that logistical demands are being met efficiently.

Lastly, this enables international exporters to enter and access the Malaysian market, fostering relationships with local businesses and broadening their reach. For several international companies, particularly small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs), it enhanced access to logistics services may be transformative, enabling them to easily transport products to Malaysia and penetrate new client markets. By assisting foreign exporters in penetrating Malaysia's market, MLP develops international business partnerships and enhances Malaysia's position as a major participant in the global supply chain.

5. FEEDBACK FROM COMMUNITY

Figure 1. Results of the survey given to UiTM students – Importance of logistic service.

According to the survey's findings, most respondents anticipate logistics services are crucial. Notably, 83.4% of respondents (46.7%) rated logistics services as "very high" and 36.7% as "high," indicating that they are crucial to their operations or business activities.

In contrast, 16.7% of respondents gave logistics services a "medium" relevance rating, indicating that although they recognize the importance, they do not see it as important as other services.

It is interesting to note that none of the respondents gave logistics services a "low" or "very low" relevance rating, indicating all respondents agree to at least moderate importance on these services.

Figure 2. Results of the survey given to UiTM students – Users' opinion.

Following that, the respondents ranked cheaper cost as the most significant element, with the majority (53.3%) choosing it as the top justification for utilizing digital platforms in logistics. It implies that when it comes to digital solutions, logistics organizations prioritize cost savings.

With 26.7%, easy to use comes in second, suggesting that cheaper cost is a more important factor than user-friendliness.

The fact that a large number of service providers is not a significant factor (13.3%) may indicate that most respondents do not view having a wide range of service providers as a major concern.

With 6.7%, increased security comes in last, indicating that although security is always crucial, it might not be the most significant factor when weighed against other advantages like cheaper cost and ease of use.

Do you think this Malaysia Logistics Platform (MLP) app would help to recognize more logistics providers that are available in Malaysia?

30 responses

Figure 3. Results of the survey given to UiTM students – Users’ opinion of MLP.

Lastly, all of the respondents (100%) think that new logistics providers in Malaysia could be found with the use of the Malaysian Logistics Platform (MLP) app. This unanimous finding implies that utilizing such a platform to find and interact with a wider variety of service providers is strongly regarded as beneficial.

The lack of negative feedback suggests that there is a strong belief in the MLP platform’s ability to improve market visibility and accessibility to logistics options.

In conclusion, this finding underlines a clear demand and acceptance for a system such as the MLP app to assist in streamlining and enhancing logistics services in Malaysia.

6. PRODUCT DETAILS

Figure 4. Step 1: Users needs to Sign in into their business MLP account using their business email.

Figure 5. Step 2: Users may create an account if they they do not have one.

Figure 6. Step 3: Users may reset password if they forgot their password.

Figure 7. Step 4: Clicking the Hamburger button displays lists of Menu

Figure 7. Step 5: Clicking the Modes of Transportation

Figure 8. Step 6: Clicking Air Freight & Logistics displays the Air button displays logistics areas company's name in selected areas

Figure 9. Step 7: Clicking AK Freight SDN BHD displays.

Figure 10. Step 8: When users clicked Select Company Button the company's profile, same goes for they are required to secure payment sea and land transportation.

7. CONCLUSION AND REFLECTION

To wrap things up, the Malaysia Logistics Platform (MLP) is a unique trading application that links companies with logistics providers throughout Malaysia and provides reasonably priced shipping choices by land, sea, and air. Users sign in using business email and password, allowing users to choose transportation options and book logistical services straightforwardly. MLP improves logistical procedures, creates income via transaction fees and subscriptions, and helps the local economy by offering easily available transportation choices by effectively matching supply with demand.

Based on the findings of a survey, most of the respondents agree that logistic services are crucial, so this is why we believe that with the help of MLP, it streamlines company logistics by giving quick access to sea, air, or land as several means of transportation. This enables nearby companies to choose the finest logistics suppliers hassle-free. In addition to that, MLP also helps in cost savings, as the prices for services will be cheaper while maintaining quality.

Upon reflection, after considering MLP's launch and possible impact, it is clear that this platform fills an important demand in the logistics sector. MLP not only improves the operational efficiency of companies but also lessens the complexity and expense of logistics by streamlining the search and booking procedure of transportation services. Moreover, MLP's capacity to simplify worldwide trade links and promote international cooperation helps to explain its great commercial potential by means of greater company prospects and long-term supply chain relationships supporting development. All things considered, an app like MLP will be important in ensuring that the logistics sector can meet the growing needs of global commerce, promoting increased connection, operational effectiveness, and economic growth, both locally and globally.

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